

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Temirova Nigina Baxshilloyevna

HUDUDLARNI IJTIMOIIY-IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA

OTMLAR ISHTIROKINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/MAY

